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Research Article

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF SUSTAINED RELEASE MATRIX TABLETS OF VALGANCICLOVIR HYDROCHLORIDE BY USING NATURAL AND SYNTHETIC POLYMERS

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The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of sustained release matrix tablets of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride (VH) using both natural and synthetic polymers to enhance therapeutic efficacy and patient compliance. Various formulations were prepared utilizing different concentrations of Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose (HPMC), Xanthan Gum, and Karaya Gum as matrix-forming agents. The pre-compression parameters including bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio, and angle of repose were evaluated and found within acceptable limits, indicating good flow properties. Post-compression studies, such as hardness, thickness, friability, weight variation, and drug content, were also within pharmacopeial standards, confirming the uniformity and mechanical integrity of the tablets. In-vitro drug release studies were carried out for 12 hours using USP dissolution apparatus. Among all formulations, batch VH4 demonstrated a sustained and controlled drug release profile, achieving 99.14% drug release at the end of 12 hours, thereby considering the optimized formulation. This study concludes that a combination of natural and synthetic polymers can effectively control the release of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride, providing a promising approach for sustained drug delivery.

Keywords: Valganciclovir Hydrochloride, HPMC, Xanthan Gum and Karaya Gum**Corresponding author:****Sara Kausar,***M.pharm*

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INTRODUCTION:¹⁻¹⁰

Sustained release (SR) tablets are designed to release drugs slowly, maintaining uniform blood levels for prolonged therapeutic effect and better patient compliance compared to conventional forms that require multiple daily doses. The concept originated in the early 1950s with the first product, "NitroGlyn." These dosage forms—also called prolonged, modified, extended, or depot release — aim to reduce dosing frequency, localize drug action, minimize side effects, and maintain consistent plasma concentrations.

Principles and Considerations

SR formulations provide constant drug delivery and enhanced efficacy. Before designing, factors like drug half-life, pharmacological activity, and absorption mechanism must be reviewed. Matrix tablets represent an important advancement, eliminating complex manufacturing steps like coating or pelletization. Hydrophilic polymer matrices are widely used because drug release is primarily governed by the type and ratio of polymer. Matrix systems control the dissolution or diffusion of drug and are especially suited for poorly water-soluble drugs.

Rationale for Extended Release

Some drugs require multiple daily doses to sustain therapeutic levels, leading to non compliance, fluctuations in blood levels, and increased risk of toxicity or therapeutic failure. Extended-release forms overcome these issues by releasing drug gradually—often only once or twice daily producing stable plasma concentrations and reducing the need for night dosing.

Drawbacks of Conventional Dosage Forms:

- Poor compliance and frequent dosing.
- Fluctuating drug levels causing peaks (toxicity) and troughs (ineffectiveness).

Modified Release Systems include:

1. Delayed Release—Uses coating or repeat action for timed release.
2. Sustained/Controlled/ Extended Release—Provides prolonged or controlled delivery at pre determined rates.
3. Site-specific targeting—Directs drug to a particular organ or tissue.
4. Receptor targeting—Delivers drug to a specific receptor within a tissue.

Design and Formulation of Oral SR Systems

Oral SR systems rely on diffusion, dissolution, ion exchange, osmotic pressure, or pH-independent mechanisms. The goal is a near zero-order release pattern, mimicking intravenous infusion.

A. Diffusion Systems:

- *Reservoir type:* Drug core surrounded by polymer membrane (zero-order possible but

costly).

- *Matrix type:* Drug dispersed in an insoluble matrix; release depends on diffusion.
- Higuchi's equation describes release rate as proportional to \sqrt{t} .

B. Dissolution Systems:

- *Reservoir type:* Alternating layers of drug and dissolving coats produce pulsed delivery.
- *Matrix type:* Drug is incorporated in a dissolving matrix, releasing by erosion or diffusion. Hydrophilic matrix technology is favored for simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and regulatory acceptance.

Ion Exchange Systems:

Drug forms a complex with ionic resin, in the GI tract, ions (Na^+Cl^-) exchange and release the drug.

Osmotic Systems:

Water enters a semi-permeable membrane, generating pressure to pump drug solution through a small orifice.

pH-Independent Systems:

Buffering agents maintain constant internal pH for uniform release.

Altered Density Systems:

High-density pellets sink; low-density floating systems stay in the stomach longer to enhance absorption.

Matrix Tablets

Matrix tablets, made by compressing drug with polymer and excipients, provide one of the simplest controlled release methods.

METHODOLOGY:¹¹⁻¹⁶**Analytical method development:****a) Determination of absorption maxima:**

100mg of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride pure drug was dissolved in 15ml of Methanol and make up to 100ml with 0.1N HCL (stock solution-1). 10ml of above solution was taken and make up with 100ml by using 0.1 N HCL (stock solution-2 i.e., 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). From this 10ml was taken and make up with 100 ml of 0.1 N HCL (10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). Scan the 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ using Double beam UV/VIS spectrophotometer in the range of 200 – 400 nm.

b) Preparation calibration curve:

100mg of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride pure drug was dissolved in 15ml of Methanol and volume make up to 100ml with 0.1N HCL (stock solution-1) 10ml of above solution was taken and make up with 100 ml by using 0.1N HCL (Stock solution-2 i.e. 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). From this take 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1.0ml of solution and make up to 10ml with 0.1N HCL to obtain 2,4,6,8 and 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride per ml of solution. The absorbance of the above dilutions was measured at 271nm by using UV-Spectrophotometer taking 0.1N HCL as blank. Then a graph was plotted by taking Concentration

on X-Axis and Absorbance on Y-Axis which gives a straight line Linearity of standard curve was assessed from the square of correlation coefficient (R^2) which determined by least-square linear regression analysis. The above procedure was repeated by using pH 6.8 phosphate buffer solutions.

Drug-Excipient compatibility studies Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy:

Drug excipient interaction studies are significant for the successful formulation of every dosage form. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy studies were used for the assessment of physicochemical compatibility and interactions, which helps in the prediction of interaction between drug and other excipients. In the current study 1:1 ratio was used for preparation of physical mixtures used for analyzing of compatibility studies. FT-IR studies were carried out with a Bruker, ATR FTIR facility using direct sample technique.

Formulation development of Sustained release Tablets:¹⁷⁻¹⁹

All the formulations were prepared by direct compression method. The compositions of different formulations are given in Table. The tablets were prepared as per the procedure given below and aim is to prolong the release of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride.

Procedure:

- 1) Valganciclovir Hydrochloride and all other ingredients except Mg stearate and Aerosil were individually passed through sieve no #40.
- 2) Valganciclovir Hydrochloride, MCC, and polymer mix thoroughly than add the binder solution mix properly up to 15 min.
- 3) Dry the above mixture at 65-70°C by using dryer.
- 4) After completion of drying the mixture is passed through sieve no#22.
- 5) The powder mixture was lubricated with Mg stearate and Talc.
- 6) Finally go for compression.

Table 1: Formulation of Sustained release tablets

Ingredients	VH1	VH2	VH3	VH4	VH5	VH6	VH7	VH8	VH9
Valganciclovir Hydrochloride	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
HPMCK 15	50	75	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
Xanthan Gum	-	-	-	50	75	100	-	-	-
Guargum	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	75	100
PVPK30	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Talc	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Mgstearate	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
MCC	255	230	205	255	230	205	255	230	205
Total weight	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450	450

Evaluation Parameters²⁰⁻²⁸

Pre Compression parameters Bulk density(DB)

Bulk density is the ratio between a given mass of the powder and its bulk volume.

Bulk density=Mass of Powder/Bulk volume of the powder Bulk density

(DB) = W /V0

Procedure: An accurately weighed quantity of granules (w) (which was previously passed through sieve No: 40) was carefully transferred into 250 ml measuring cylinder and measure the bulk volume.

Tapped Density (DT)

Tapped density is the ratio between a given mass of

powder (or) granules and the constant (or) fixed volume of powder or granules after tapping.

Tapped density=mass of the powder/tapped volume

Procedure: An accurately weighed quantity of granules (w) (which was previously passed through sieve No:40) was carefully transferred in to 250ml measuring cylinder and the cylinder was tapped on a wooden surface from the height of 2.5 cm at two second intervals. The tapping was continued until no further change in volume (until a constant volume) was obtained(Vf). The tapped density was calculated by using the formula

Tapped density (DT) =W/Vf

Hausner's ratio

Hausner's ratio is an indirect index of ease of powder flow and was calculated by the

formula,

Hausner's ratio=DT/DB

Where, DT is the tapped density DB is the bulk density

Compressibility index

Compressibility index (CI) was determined by measuring the initial volume (V_0) and final volume (V_f) after hundred tapping's of a sample in a measuring cylinder. It indicates the powder flow properties and expressed in terms of percentage and given in table no. 14 and calculated by using the formula

$$\% \text{Compressibility index} = \frac{V_0 - V_f}{V_0} \times 100$$

Angle of repose

Angle of repose⁶² was measured by fixed funnel method. It determines flow property of the powder. It is defined as maximum angle formed between the surface of the pile of powder and the horizontal plane.

The powder was allowed to flow through the funnel fixed to a stand at definite height (h). By measuring the height and radius of the heap of powder formed (r), angle of repose was calculated by using formula given below and the calculated values obtained was shown in table no. 14

$\theta = \tan^{-1}(h / r)$ Where, θ is the angle of repose h is the height in cm r is the radius in cm

Post Compression parameters Weight variation test

Twenty tablets were randomly selected and weighed, to estimate the average weight and that were compared with individual tablet weight. The percentage weight variation was calculated as per Indian Pharmacopoeial Specification. Tablets with an average weight 250 mg so the % deviation was $\pm 5\%$.

Friability test

Twenty tablets were weighed and subjected to drum of friability test apparatus. The drum rotated at a speed of 25rpm. The friabilator was operated for 4 minutes and reweighed the tablets.

% loss (F) was calculated by the following formula. $F = 100 (W_0 - W) / W_0$

Where W_0 = Initial weight = Final weight

Hardness test

The hardness of tablets was measured by using Monsanto hardness tester. The results were complies with IP specification.

Thickness test

The rule of physical dimension of the tablets such as sizes and thickness is necessary for consumer

acceptance and maintain tablet uniformity. The dimensional specifications were measured by using screw gauge.

The thickness of the tablet is mostly related to the tablet hardness can be used as initial control parameter.

Drug content

The amount of drug in tablet was important for monitor from tablet to tablet, and batch to batch is to evaluate for efficacy of tablets. For this test, take ten tablets from each batch were weighed and powdered. Weighed equivalent to the average weight of the tablet powder and transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in a suitable quantity of media. The solution was made up to the mark and mixed well. Then filter the solution. A portion of the filtrate sample was analyzed by UV spectrophotometer.

In vitro drug release studies

Apparatus	--	USP-II,
Paddle Method	--	
Dissolution Medium	--	0.1N HCL,
pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer RPM	--	50
Sampling intervals (hrs)	--	
1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11 and 12hrs.	--	Temperature $37^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$

Procedure:

900ml of 0.1 HCL was placed in vessel and the USP apparatus –II (Paddle Method) was assembled. The media was allowed to equilibrate to temp of $37^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. Tablet was placed in the vessel and apparatus was operated for 2 hours. Then 0.1 N HCL was replaced with pH 6.8 phosphate buffer and process was continued up to 24 hrs at 50 rpm. At specific time intervals, withdrawn 5 ml of sample and again 5ml media was added to maintain the sink condition. Withdrawn samples were analyzed at 271 nm wavelength of drug using UV-spectrophotometer.

Application of Release Rate Kinetics to Dissolution Data

Various models were tested for explaining the kinetics of drug release. To analyze the mechanism of the drug release rate kinetics of the dosage form, the obtained data were fitted into zero-order, first order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas release model.

Zero order release rate kinetics:

To study the zero-order release kinetics the release rate data are fitted to the following equation.

$$F=K_0t$$

Where, 'F' is the drug release at time 't', and 'K₀' is the zero order release rate constant. The plot of % drug release versus time is linear.

First order release rate kinetics: The release rate data are fitted to the following equation

$$\text{Log (100-F)} =kt$$

A plot of log cumulative percent of drug remaining to be released vs. time is plotted the nit gives first order release.

Higuchi release model: To study the Higuchi release kinetics, the release rate data were fitted to the following equation.

$$F =kt^{1/2}$$

Where, 'k' is the Higuchi constant.

In higuchi model, a plot % drug release versus square root of time is linear.

Korsmeyer and Peppas release model:

The mechanism of drug release was evaluated by plotting the log percentage of drug released versus log time according to Korsmeyer-

Peppasequation. The exponent 'n' indicates the mechanism of drug release calculated through the slope of the straight Line.

$$M_t/M_\infty=Kt^n$$

Where, M_t/M_∞ is fraction of drug released at time 't', k represents a constant, and 'n' is the diffusional exponent, which characterizes the type of release mechanism during the dissolution process. For non-Fickian release, the value of n falls between 0.5 and 1.0; while in case of Fickian diffusion, n=0.5; for zero-order release (case II transport), n=1; and for super case II transport, n >1. In this model, a plot of log (M_t/M_∞) versus log (time) is linear.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

The present study was aimed to develop sustained release tablets of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride using various polymers. All the formulations were evaluated for physicochemical properties and *in vitro* drug release studies.

Analytical Method

Graphs of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride were taken in 0.1NHCL and in pH6.8 phosphate buffer at 251 nm and 254 nm respectively.

Table 2: Observations for graph of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride in 0.1NHCL

Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
0	0
2	0.124
4	0.236
6	0.346
8	0.459
10	0.574

Fig 1: Standard curve of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride

Table 3: Standard graph values of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride at 254nm in pH6.8 phosphate buffer

Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
0	0
2	0.127
4	0.242
6	0.359
8	0.477
10	0.591

Fig 2: Standard curve of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride**Preformulation parameters of powder blend****Table 4: Pre-formulation parameters of Core blend**

Formulation code	Angle of repose(Θ)	Bulk density (gm/cm^3)	Tapped density(gm/cm^3)	Carr's Index (%)	Hausner's ratio
VH1	26.45 \pm 0.6	0.54 \pm 0.02	0.65 \pm 0.04	16.92 \pm 0.04	1.2 \pm 0.07
VH2	25.12 \pm 0.51	0.48 \pm 0.09	0.57 \pm 0.05	15.78 \pm 0.05	1.18 \pm 0.06
VH3	27.08 \pm 0.47	0.58 \pm 0.01	0.69 \pm 0.05	15.94 \pm 0.01	1.18 \pm 0.04
VH4	28.12 \pm 0.35	0.56 \pm 0.03	0.66 \pm 0.02	15.15 \pm 0.02	1.17 \pm 0.05
VH5	25.24 \pm 0.52	0.53 \pm 0.02	0.65 \pm 0.05	18.46 \pm 0.09	1.22 \pm 0.07
VH6	25.33 \pm 0.48	0.54 \pm 0.05	0.64 \pm 0.04	15.62 \pm 0.05	1.18 \pm 0.08
VH7	27.7 \pm 0.42	0.52 \pm 0.09	0.64 \pm 0.02	18.75 \pm 0.09	1.23 \pm 0.06
VH8	26.8 \pm 0.35	0.56 \pm 0.04	0.67 \pm 0.08	16.41 \pm 0.00	1.19 \pm 0.05
VH9	25.01 \pm 0.21	0.49 \pm 0.05	0.57 \pm 0.06	14.03 \pm 0.01	1.16 \pm 0.02

All the values represent n=3

Tablet powder blend was subjected to various pre-formulation parameters. The angle of repose values indicates that the powder blend has good flow properties. The bulk density of all the formulations was found to be in the range showing that the powder has good flow properties. The tapped density of all the formulations powders has good flow properties. The compressibility index of all the formulations was found to be below 16.19 which show that the powder has good flow properties. All the formulations have shown the Hausner ratio below 1.19 indicating the powder has good flow properties.

Quality Control Parameters for tablets:

Tablet quality control tests such as weight variation, hardness, friability, thickness and drug release studies in different media were performed on the compression table

Table 5: *In vitro* quality control parameters for tablets

Formulation codes	Weight variation (mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%loss)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)
VH1	448.28	4.12	0.36	3.56	98.76
VH2	451.36	4.37	0.22	3.48	99.44
VH3	447.22	4.25	0.18	3.51	97.39
VH4	450.47	4.08	0.12	3.44	99.25
VH5	455.88	4.29	0.34	3.61	99.71
VH6	446.34	4.34	0.28	3.59	98.34
VH7	449.86	4.38	0.39	3.44	101.29
VH8	447.25	4.19	0.27	3.49	97.52
VH9	451.47	4.22	0.36	3.52	99.33

Weight variation test:

Tablets of each batch were subjected to weight variation test, difference in weight and percent deviation was calculated for each tablet. The average weight of the tablet is approximately in range of 447.22 to 455.88mg, so the permissible limit is(>450 mg). The results of the test showed that, the tablet weights were within limit.

Hardness test:

Hardness of the three tablet so each batch was checked by using Pfizer hardness tester and the data's were shown in Table8.4. The results showed that the hardness of the tablets is in range of 4.12 to 4.38 kg/cm², which was within IP limits.

Thickness:

Thickness of three tablets of each batch was checked by using Micrometer and data shown in

Table-5. The result showed that thickness of the tablet is raging from 3.44 to 3.61mm.

Friability:

Tablets of each batch were evaluated for percentage friability and the data were shown in the Table 5. The average friability of all the formulations was less than 1% as per official requirement of IP indicating a good mechanical resistance of tablets.

Drug content:

Drug content studies were performed for the prepared formulations. From the drug content studies it was concluded that all the formulations were showing the% drug content values within 97.39 101.29%.

All the parameters such as weight variation, friability, hardness, thickness and drug content were found to be within limits.

Table 6: Dissolution Data of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride Tablets

TIME	CUMULATIVE % OF DRUG RELEASE								
	VH1	VH2	VH3	VH4	VH5	VH6	VH7	VH8	VH9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	26.23	21.41	22.36	18.12	20.54	17.36	27.54	24.02	16.82
2	35.35	28.65	29.25	37.64	26.22	28.55	32.11	28.53	21.59
3	48.09	35.53	33.13	43.20	32.13	34.12	41.56	35.41	26.15
4	52.69	44.25	39.52	49.56	38.28	43.69	48.37	38.57	28.23
5	58.41	49.57	46.87	56.43	44.74	49.11	53.64	44.98	34.69
6	63.58	51.45	53.71	59.01	51.44	58.82	59.21	47.61	38.87
7	74.29	62.62	58.97	68.57	55.52	63.17	63.95	56.57	45.53
8	81.14	67.95	63.72	74.91	59.39	69.43	72.41	62.11	52.26
9	89.16	71.41	75.46	79.41	64.62	75.89	79.89	65.76	57.34
10	92.17	74.54	79.78	84.72	76.54	82.47	84.42	69.43	62.22
11	96.33	82.75	86.01	87.02	81.63	89.21	88.27	77.04	71.01
12	97.22	96.81	97.46	99.14	96.74	98.58	93.41	86.81	83.61

Fig 3: Dissolution profile of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride (VH1, VH2, VH3 formulations)

Fig 4: Dissolution profile of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride (VH4, VH5, VH6 formulations)

Fig. 5: Dissolution profile of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride (VH7, VH8, VH9 formulations)

The formulations prepared with HPMC K 15 showed good retardation capacity of drug release (97.46 %) up to 12 hours in concentration 100mg whereas high concentrations (retard the drug release up to 12 hours).

The formulations prepared with Xanthan Gum showed good retardation capacity of drug release (99.14%) up to 12 hours in concentration 50 mg whereas high concentrations (retard the drug release up to 12 hours).

The formulations prepared with Guar gum showed good retardation capacity of drug release (93.41%) up to 12 hours in concentration 50mg whereas high concentrations (retard the drug release up to 12 hours).

Hence from the abovedissolution data it was concludedthat VH4 formulation was considered as optimized

formulation because good drug release (99.14 %) in 12 hours.

Optimised formulation VH4 was kept for release kinetic studies. From the above graphs it was evident that the formulation VH4 was followed Higuchi release kinetics mechanism.

Drug-Excipient compatibility studies

Fig. 6: FT-TR Spectrum of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride pure drug

Fig. 7: FT-IR Spectrum of Optimized Formulation

There was no disappearance of any characteristics peak in the FTIR spectrum of drug and the polymer used. This shows that there is no chemical interaction between the drug and the polymers used. The presence of peaks at the expected range confirms that the materials taken for the study are genuine and there were no possible interactions. Valganciclovir Hydrochloride is also present in the physical mixture, which indicates that there is no interaction between drug and the polymers, which confirms the stability of the drug.

CONCLUSION:

The present study focused on the formulation and evaluation of sustained release matrix tablets of Valganciclovir Hydrochloride using both natural and synthetic polymers. All pre-compression and post-compression parameters of the prepared formulations were found to be within the acceptable limits as per Indian Pharmacopoeia (IP) standards, indicating good flow properties and tablet integrity. Among the various

formulations developed, VH4 emerged as the optimized formulation, demonstrating a sustained and controlled drug release of 99.14% over a 12-hour period. This sustained release profile suggests that VH4 can effectively maintain therapeutic drug levels for an extended duration, potentially improving patient compliance and treatment efficacy. Overall, the study successfully highlights the potential of using a combination of natural and synthetic polymers in developing an efficient sustained release drug delivery system for Valganciclovir Hydrochloride.

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